

ISic3069

I.Sicily inscription 3069

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific (?)

Material

terracotta

Object

tabula

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Phintias

Place of origin (modern)

Licata

Provenance

Contrada S. Antonino, Licata

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale
Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory 1562

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 15 cm

Width 19 cm

Depth 3.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 20 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ου (vac.undefined) καλ
2. [---]τες εις

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1990

Translation

Commentary

Manganaro 1990: 407 suggests that the final three letters of line 1, following the vacat, are a demotic-type abbreviation, as found in other Hellenistic epigraphy in Sicily

Digital identifiers:

TM 645422

EDCS 64400328

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 40.0805

Manganaro, G. 1990. Metoikismos-metaphora di poleis in Sicilia: il caso dei Gelo di Phintias e la relativa documentazione epigrafica. *Annali della scuola normale superiore di Pisa*. 20: 391-408. At 407 and tav.LXXXIV

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